

Structural/microstructural, magnetic and optical studies on Mn-doped BiFeO₃ thin films

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The complex perovskite structures and the most promising magnetoelectric (ME) materials bismuth ferrite BiFeO₃ (BFO) have attracted significant attentions over the last few decades due to the coexistence of ferroelectric and antiferromagnetic order at comparatively high transition temperatures $T_C \sim 1125$ K and $T_N \sim 645$ K respectively [1-5]. The paper reports the studies on the structural, microstructural, optical and magnetic properties of BiFe_{1-x}Mn_xO₃ with ($x = 0.0, 0.02, 0.05$) thin films prepared by spray pyrolysis method. The powder x-ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns show a structural phase transformation from rhombohedral structure ($\mathbf{a}=\mathbf{b}= 5.5694$ Å and $\mathbf{c} = 6.8927$ Å) with R3m space group for the Mn-doped BiFe_{1-x}Mn_xO₃ ($x=0.00$ & 0.02) thin films to distorted orthorhombic (monoclinic) structure ($\mathbf{a}= 5.79$ Å, $\mathbf{b}= 5.6899$ Å and $\mathbf{c}= 4.1739$ Å) with Cm space group for BiFe_{1-x}Mn_xO₃ ($x=0.05$) thin films. The average crystallite size of BiFe_{1-x}Mn_xO₃ was calculated using Debye-Scherrer formula and found to change from 18 nm ($x=0$) to 43 nm ($x=0.05$). The microstructural strains calculated from Williamson-Hall plot for the prepared BiFe_{1-x}Mn_xO₃ with ($x = 0.0, 0.02, 0.05$) thin films were found to vary from 0.07576 to 0.00134. The surface morphology of the as prepared films examined by atomic force microscopy (AFM) show that spherical particle (~ 100 nm) are densely packed with sharp grain boundary. The local magnetic domain structures of strip-like for the pure and Mn-doped BFO thin film were explored by magnetic force microscopy (MFM). The optical band gap obtained from UV-Vis absorption spectra for the BiFe_{1-x}Mn_xO₃ with ($x = 0.0, 0.02, 0.05$) films were also found to vary in the range of 3.479 eV to 3.386 eV.

Thin films; AFM; MFM; TEM; UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy.

References

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